

Can a brief educational programme affect Chinese American mental health providers' attitudes towards psychedelics?

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There is a growing body of literature on the therapeutic applications of psychedelics, particularly within Psychedelic Assisted Psychotherapy (PAP). PAP is strongly shaped by set and setting, both of which are influenced by cultural factors. To explore Chinese American mental health providers' attitudes toward psychedelics and the effect of educational training, we conducted an online survey following a one hour educational session on PAP delivered within a professional peer support group. Seventeen members participated, and fourteen pre- and post-training self ratings were compared. Before the session, concerns about safety, dependence, and misuse were common. After the training, safety concerns decreased markedly, although worries about misuse remained. Participants also reported barriers to referring patients for PAP, including issues related to patient safety and expectations, financial constraints such as cost and insurance coverage, and the level of responsibility placed on the provider. Stigma surrounding psychedelics and perceptions of insufficient research evidence were also noted as obstacles to adopting PAP in practice. The findings suggest that while Chinese American providers remain cautious about psychedelics, even a brief educational intervention can increase receptivity toward PAP. This highlights the importance of targeted educational programmes that offer culturally sensitive information and evidence about psychedelics and PAP, particularly for providers working in diverse cultural contexts.

Keywords: Chinese American; educational training; perceived barriers; psychedelic assisted psychotherapy; psychedelics

The contemporary resurgence of interest in psychedelics has produced a substantial and expanding body of literature regarding their therapeutic applications, alongside a growing number of providers offering psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy (PAP). Despite this increasing attention, research focusing on American psychiatrists' attitudes towards PAP remains limited, and interventions which may influence these attitudes have not been studied in subgroups such as Chinese-American clinicians, with Asian respondents comprising 3%–6% of the large survey respondents in mental health and among general healthcare practitioners (Kucsera, 2023; Wang et al., 2024).

Two pivotal national survey studies conducted by Barnett et al. have contributed significantly to understanding these perspectives. The initial survey was conducted in 2016 (Barnett et al., 2018), and repeated after a seven-year interval (Barnett et al., 2023), revealing a substantial positive shift in the attitudes of American psychiatrists. Notably, a majority of respondents indicated an intention to incorporate PAP into their practice pending regulatory approval.

Other investigations corroborate this trend of increasing acceptance, with acknowledgement of reservations about this novel treatment. For example, Barnett and colleagues conducted an informal, anonymous survey of psychiatrists attending psychedelic-focused presentations at two national conferences in the United States found widespread belief in the therapeutic potential of psychedelics, while identifying key concerns—insufficient numbers of trained providers, logistical barriers to PAP delivery, patient contraindications, and risks of diversion (Barnett et al., 2022). Qualitative research utilising semi-structured interviews with 30 therapists further highlighted apprehensions regarding commercialisation, power imbalances in the therapeutic relationship, misunderstandings, cost and accessibility, and the potential for diversion (Earleywine et al., 2022). A national survey of psychologists reflected cautiously favourable views toward PAP, with over 80% of respondents supporting further research and only 17% expressing the belief that psychedelics are unsafe even under controlled medical supervision (Davis et al., 2022).

PAP's integration into clinical practice is influenced by a complex interplay of cultural, scientific, technological, and policy factors, and its acceptance varies markedly across cultures and time periods. For example, Native American religious ceremonies incorporate peyote, while ayahuasca is central to healing traditions in the Amazon basin. In ancient China, hallucinogenic plants such as *Caesalpinia decapetala* (*yunshi*) were used for ritualistic purposes (Li, 1977). The most prominent cultural shift toward mainstream adoption of psychedelics has occurred in Western societies, as evidenced by the founding of the Multidisciplinary Association of Psychedelic Studies (MAPS) in 1985 and a subsequent series of studies investigating MDMA-assisted therapy (Mitchell et al., 2021; Mithoefer et al., 2013; Oehen et al., 2013; Smith et al., 2022). This evolution from the initial wave of Western psychedelic use to the current research renaissance has profoundly shaped public and professional perceptions in the United States. Importantly, most clinical studies have enrolled predominantly White participants, limiting the generalisability of findings. A 2018 review of inclusion of people of colour in PAP research found that 82.3% of participants across 18 studies were White (non-Hispanic), with only 1.8% identifying as of Asian ancestry (Michaels et al., 2018). By contrast, the 2020 US Census reported that 19.9 million individuals, or 6.0% of the population, identify as Asian American, with Chinese Americans representing the largest subgroup (Budiman & Ruiz, 2021).

Clinically, psychedelics are typically administered within the context of psychotherapy – referred to as PAP – which emphasises the importance of “set” (the patient's mindset and attitude) and “setting” (the environment in which the intervention is delivered) (Hartogsohn, 2017). Cultural factors are highly influential in shaping both set and setting (Ching et al., 2023; Neitzke-Spruill, 2019; Williams et al., 2021). However, little is known about the impact of culture on attitudes towards psychedelics, or whether mental health providers from minority backgrounds share similar levels of acceptance regarding the clinical use of these substances (Relojo, 2018).

Given that Asian cultures, including Chinese, tend to adopt more conservative views toward psychoactive substances, Chinese American mental health providers may differ from their mainstream counterparts in their attitudes toward psychedelics and PAP.

This study aims to address two primary questions: (1) What are the attitudes of Chinese American mental health providers toward PAP, including the perceived barriers to referring patients for or personally providing PAP? (2) Does education or training influence these providers' perceptions of PAP and their willingness to refer patients for or incorporate PAP into their practice?

METHODS

Table 1. Outline of the presentation contents.

Section number	Section topic
I	Overview of psychedelics
II	Historical context of psychedelic research
III	Current "second wave" of psychedelic research
IV	Overview of psychedelic assisted psychotherapy (PAP)
V	Effects of psychedelics on brain function and ego dissolution
VI	Application of ketamine in psychiatry
VII	Challenges in the use of psychedelics and PAP
VIII	Conclusions

The participants of this study were members of an online peer-support group comprising 151 Chinese American mental health providers with prescription privileges practicing in the United States. The group members included psychiatrists, residents, fellows, and advanced practice providers such as nurse practitioners. A one-hour online training was delivered by a clinician trained in PAP (see Table 1 for the presentation outline). The training covered the historical use of psychedelics in mental health, potential mechanisms of action, the PAP practice model, clinical applications, and relevant evidence from the medical literature. Their programme was announced approximately 2 months prior to the training and multiple reminders were issued prior to the session. Participants were encouraged to attend and no prior registration was required. Thirty providers attended the online session.

Following the training, an online post-training survey was administered. Seven weeks after the session, all group members were invited to complete a survey assessing attitudes toward psychedelics; responses may have been affected by recall bias due to this extended interval. Attendees of the educational seminar were asked to report their attitudes both before and after the training, while non-attendees were instructed to select 'NA' for post-training items.

The survey was composed of 11 multiple-choice questions asking providers' opinions on psychedelics and PAP. To develop survey items assessing Chinese American mental health providers' attitudes toward PAP, we drew on validated constructs from existing literature to ensure psychometric rigor and cultural relevance. National surveys of psychiatrists and psychologists (Barnett et al., 2018, 2022, 2023; Davis et al., 2022) informed items measuring perceived therapeutic potential, safety concerns, and barriers to PAP adoption. Qualitative thematic analysis from semi-structured interviews (Earleywine et al., 2022) further supported item development, with iterative feedback from focus groups with Chinese American providers ensuring cultural sensitivity. The first nine questions each comprised two sub-questions addressing perceptions of PAP before and after the training. Responses were recorded using a five-point Likert scale ('Strongly disagree' to 'Strongly agree'), with an additional 'Don't know/NA' option. The final two questions addressed perceived barriers, allowing for both multiple-choice and free-text responses. Group members who did not attend the training were also encouraged to complete the survey, though their data were not excluded from the final analysis. No personal identifying information was collected.

For those who attended the training, Wilcoxon rank sum tests were used to compare pre- and post-training opinions about psychedelics, with an alpha of 0.05 used as the cutoff for statistical significance. Data were analysed using SPSS version 29. The study protocol was submitted to the Stanford Institutional Review Board (IRB) and exempted, as the survey was intended for programme improvement and did not collect personally identifiable information. Despite the exemption, the

study addressed sensitive topics, such as provider attitudes toward the clinical use of psychedelics. To minimise potential risks, all responses were collected anonymously, participation was voluntary, and electronic informed consent was obtained at the start of the survey. Participants were advised of their right to skip questions or withdraw at any time without penalty. The survey was carefully designed to avoid stigmatising language, and multiple safeguards were implemented to protect participant confidentiality and reduce psychological or professional risk.

RESULTS

Participant overview and survey response rates

A total of 30 individuals attended the training session. Of these, 17 participants completed the online survey. Among the 17 survey respondents, three did not attend the training session; data from these individuals were excluded from the final analysis. The overall response rate among the broader professional group (which included 151 members, both attendees and non-attendees) was 11.3% (17 out of 151). The response rate among training attendees was higher, at 46.7% (14 out of 30). Consequently, pre- and post-training comparisons were conducted using data from the remaining 14 participants who attended the session.

Attitude shifts following a one-hour training

Prior to the training, a substantial proportion of respondents expressed concerns about psychedelics and PAP. Specifically, 50.0% believed that using psychedelics is unsafe and presents a high risk of dependence, while 56.3% considered psychedelics highly likely to be misused. Furthermore, 87.5% indicated that they would not be willing to incorporate PAP into their own practice. Only 37.5% considered PAP a potential therapeutic tool, and just 18.8% viewed it as an appropriate clinical intervention.

Following the one-hour online training, respondents demonstrated significantly more favourable attitudes (as detailed in Table 2 and Figure 1). Post-training, 71.4% agreed that PAP could be a potential therapeutic tool. Nearly 57.1% reported feeling knowledgeable about PAP – an increase from 6.3% pre-training – and were open to considering its clinical application (up from 18.8% pre-training) and willing to refer patients to PAP (up from 12.5% pre-training). Additionally, 21.4% of respondents felt comfortable and knowledgeable enough to integrate psychedelic treatments into their practice, compared to 0% before the training. All Wilcoxon tests indicated statistical significance, except for the item concerning attitudes toward the likelihood of psychedelic misuse, which approached significance ($p = 0.06$).

Table 2
Respondent agreement with opinion statements pre- and post-training and comparisons

Statement	Moderately or Strongly Disagree n/N (%)	Neutral n/N (%)	Moderately or Strongly Agree n/N (%)	Don't Know/NA n/N (%)	Wilcoxon Test
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre
1. I would say I am knowledgeable about psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy (PAP).	10/16 (62.5%)	1/14 (7.1%)	5/16 (31.3%)	5/14 (35.7%)	1/16 (6.3%)
2. Psychedelics (e.g., LSD, Psilocybin, MDMA, ayahuasca) have a high risk of dependence.	5/16 (31.3%)	7/14 (50.0%)	3/16 (18.8%)	3/14 (21.4%)	8/16 (50.0%)
3. Psychedelics are highly likely to be misused.	4/16 (25.0%)	7/14 (50.0%)	3/16 (18.8%)	2/14 (14.3%)	9/16 (56.3%)
4. Taking psychedelics is unsafe.	6/16 (37.5%)	9/14 (64.3%)	2/16 (12.5%)	2/14 (14.3%)	8/16 (50.0%)
5. PAP can be a potential therapeutic tool for my patients.	3/16 (18.8%)	2/14 (14.3%)	7/16 (43.8%)	2/14 (14.3%)	6/16 (37.5%)
6. I would feel comfortable and knowledgeable to discuss PAP with a patient.	11/16 (68.8%)	5/14 (35.7%)	4/16 (25.0%)	3/14 (21.4%)	1/16 (6.3%)
7. I would consider using PAP as a clinical intervention for patients with appropriate indications.	9/16 (56.3%)	3/14 (21.4%)	4/16 (25.0%)	3/14 (21.4%)	3/16 (18.8%)
8. I would be willing to refer my patients to PAP.	7/16 (43.8%)	2/14 (14.3%)	7/16 (43.8%)	4/14 (28.6%)	2/16 (12.5%)
9. I feel comfortable and knowledgeable to adopt psychedelics treatment in my own practice.	14/16 (87.5%)	7/14 (50.0%)	2/16 (12.5%)	4/14 (28.6%)	0 (0%)

Figure 1
Respondent agreement before and after training

The survey assessed respondents' attitudes toward psychedelics and Psychedelic Assisted Psychotherapy across several dimensions. These included comfort and knowledge of PAP (Q1 on knowledge of PAP, Q6 and Q9 on comfort discussing PAP with patients and incorporating it into practice), views related to destigmatisation of psychedelics (Q2 on dependence risk, Q3 on misuse risk, Q4 on perceived safety), and willingness to incorporate or refer to PAP (Q5 on PAP as a potential therapeutic tool, Q7 on willingness to use PAP clinically, and Q8 on willingness to refer patients).

Table 3
Summary of answers to question 10 (What barriers do you see with referring patients to PAP?)

Barrier	n	%
Patient safety and expectations	14	87.5%
Cost/insurance coverage	12	75.0%
Provider responsibility	11	68.8%
Stigma associated with psychedelic use	7	43.8%
Staff/institutional resistance	6	37.5%
Lack of research evidence support	6	37.5%

Regarding barriers to patient referral (see Table 3), the most frequently cited concerns were patient safety and expectations (87.5%), cost or insurance coverage (75.0%), provider responsibility (68.8%), stigma associated with psychedelic use (43.8%), staff or institutional resistance (37.5%), and lack of research evidence (37.5%). Additional barriers reported included patient age and lack of availability.

Table 4
Summary of answers to question 11. What barriers do you see with implementing PAP in your practice?

Barrier	n	%
Provider responsibility	13	81.3%
Patient safety and expectations	10	62.5%
Cost/insurance coverage	10	62.5%
Stigma associated with psychedelic use	6	37.5%
Lack of research evidence support	6	37.5%
Staff/institutional resistance	4	25.0%

For barriers to implementing PAP in the respondents' own practices (see Table 4), the most commonly reported issues were provider responsibility (81.3%), patient safety and expectations (62.5%), cost or insurance coverage (62.5%), stigma associated with psychedelic use (37.5%), lack of supporting research evidence (37.5%), and staff or institutional resistance (25.0%). One respondent also identified lack of first-hand experience as a barrier.

DISCUSSION

We conducted an online survey of a convenience sample of Chinese American mental health providers who were members of a professional peer support group, following a one-hour online lecture focused on psychedelics and psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy (PAP). The training session resulted in improvements in provider perceptions regarding the safety and efficacy of PAP.

It is important to note that this training was delivered subsequent to ongoing, intensive discussions within the peer support group since early 2023. Throughout these discussions, multiple group members articulated questions, concerns, and interests spanning topics such as clinical trials, patient referrals to both research and clinical interventions, and personal experiences with PAP in clinical practice. Collectively, these interactions highlighted a growing interest in PAP among group members, mirroring broader trends observed in the United States, while also revealing a wide spectrum of attitudes toward psychedelics and PAP in this population.

Based on the survey data, notable shifts in provider attitudes toward psychedelics and PAP were observed. Prior to the training, respondents reported substantial concerns regarding the safety and risks of psychedelic use, including potential misuse and dependence. Although an expanding body of literature suggests that psychedelics may be used safely within established practice guidelines (Johnson et al., 2008), most respondents did not previously consider PAP a viable therapeutic tool for their patients. The majority indicated discomfort and a lack of knowledge in discussing PAP with patients and were generally unwilling to refer or adopt PAP in their clinical practice. Following the training, concerns related to safety significantly diminished, with only a minority of respondents maintaining such reservations. However, concerns about the likelihood of misuse did not show statistically significant change between pre- and post-training surveys, suggesting that, while perceptions of general safety and risk of dependence were positively affected, apprehension about misuse persisted.

Comparative analysis with a 2023 national survey of psychiatrists (Barnett et al., 2023) revealed that our sample displayed more conservative attitudes toward psychedelics. For instance, in the national survey, only 9.9% of psychiatrists agreed with the statement, "Hallucinogens are unsafe to use, even under medical supervision," whereas in our sample, 50.0% of respondents agreed with the statement, "Taking psychedelics is unsafe" prior to training; this figure declined to 21.4% post-training. Furthermore, whereas 50.4% of psychiatrists in the national survey indicated willingness to incorporate hallucinogen-assisted therapy into their practice if federally approved, none of the providers in our sample endorsed comfort or sufficient knowledge to adopt psychedelic treatments prior to training; this increased to 21.4% post-training. Notably, a greater proportion of providers expressed willingness to refer patients to PAP than to directly integrate it into their own practice, a pattern that persisted after the training. The training was effective in significantly increasing both willingness to refer and to incorporate PAP, underscoring potential cultural influences on attitudes and acceptance.

Findings from this study underscore the influence of cultural psychology on the perspectives of Chinese American mental health professionals regarding PAP. Cultural values such as collectivism, stigma, and family orientation play pivotal roles. Within Chinese and broader East Asian contexts, social harmony, filial piety, and concerns about "face" contribute to heightened scepticism toward psychedelics, particularly due to their historical association with recreational use and perceived risk (Fogg et al., 2021; Leong & Lau, 2001). Stigmatisation of mental illness and unconventional

treatments may further amplify hesitancy, given the potential for familial shame (Zane & Yeh, 2002). Systemic barriers – including limited insurance coverage and the underrepresentation of individuals of Asian origin in PAP studies (1.8% of participants from 1993 to 2017; Michaels et al., 2018) – reinforce this caution through a lack of culturally relevant evidence. Asian American mental health frameworks advocate for culturally tailored interventions that address specific psychopathology presentations (e.g., somatic symptoms) and structural obstacles such as cost and access (Alegría et al., 2004). These frameworks suggest educational programming should target stigma and collectivism, while promoting inclusive research to enhance PAP's applicability within Chinese American communities (Williams & Labate, 2019).

The most frequently identified barriers to patient referral were patient safety and expectations, cost/insurance coverage, and provider responsibility. For integrating PAP into clinical practice, the order of the top three barriers was: provider responsibility, followed by patient safety and expectations, and then cost/insurance coverage. These findings suggest that providers may prefer to refer patients rather than incorporate PAP into their own practice due to perceived lack of preparedness, greater responsibility, and logistical complexities, such as insurance considerations. These insights have implications for the development of future educational programmes and support systems aimed at reducing barriers within the healthcare system, particularly regarding these dimensions.

Several limitations should be noted. First, the use of a convenience sample recruited after an online lecture, combined with a low response rate and small sample size, introduces risks of selection bias and limits generalisability. For instance, the voluntary nature of participation may have attracted providers with stronger or more favourable opinions regarding psychedelics and PAP, resulting in a non-representative sample. Additionally, the limited sample size constrained the analysis to an exploratory rather than a confirmatory approach; thus, findings should be interpreted with caution. Future research should aim to recruit more diverse and representative samples using broader recruitment strategies. Second, survey data were collected seven weeks post-lecture, introducing the possibility of recall bias. Lastly, the one-hour lecture was not a standardised didactic session, reflecting the nascent state of PAP-specific educational programming; an outline of the presentation is provided (Table 1) to guide future curriculum development. Although some relevant training programmes exist, there remains a lack of standardised programmes or board certifications in PAP at present.

CONCLUSION

These findings underscore the importance of providing educational programmes to mental health providers, especially to those from diverse cultures, and including diverse racial and ethnic groups to improve the generalisability of PAP research outcomes, particularly groups who may experience culturally based lack of acceptance of compounds that may carry cultural stigma.

Research with larger sample sizes and broader participant pools could uncover more information and improve the generalisability of findings. The present study further highlights the possibility for a brief culturally targeted educational intervention to shift clinician attitudes regarding the safety of psychedelic-assisted therapy and comfort with referring clients to this investigational treatment.

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